

SYNTHESIS OF ACETYLENE ALCOHOLS IN DIFFERENT CATALYTIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract: In this study, with the participation of such complex catalytic systems as 3,3'-Ph₂BINOL-2Li/Ti(OⁱPr)₄/Et₂Zn and Zn(OTf)₂/TBAF•3H₂O, some ketones with a carbonyl group in the molecule - cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone, camphor, adamantanone, methyl butyl ketone, methyl ethyl ketone, methyl isopropyl ketone, methyl tert-butyl ketone, acetophenone, methyl *p*-tolyl ketone, methyl mesityl ketone, methyl β -naphthyl ketone, methyl furyl ketone, methyl thienyl ketone, methyl pyridinyl ketone and methyl 2-chlorothiophenyl ketone terminal alkynes – acetylene, hexine, octine and phenylacetylene by alkynylation reaction acetylene alcohols with high biological activity were synthesized. The relative efficiency of acetylenic alcohols synthesis was established based on the structure, nature, and chemical activity of ketone molecules, the nucleophilic addition reaction of ketones, and their influence on the product yield. The process of synthesizing acetylenic alcohols in selected systems and the factors affecting the reaction, such as temperature, reaction duration, catalyst, promoter and solvent nature, quantities of reagents and substrates, types and quantities of intermediate and by-products, were systematically studied and analyzed based on the obtained results. The activation energies of the performed reactions were determined, and the kinetics of chemical changes were analyzed. The efficiency, selectivity, and stability of catalytic systems were determined, and a relative catalytic efficiency sequence was proposed based on their influence on the reaction and product yield. The purity and structure of the synthesized compounds were investigated using modern physical and chemical research methods, specific constants were determined, and energetic and quantum chemical characteristics were calculated, including the charges of atoms in the molecules, electron density, and optical properties. The synthesized acetylenic alcohols were also applied in practice as components for anti-foaming agents in oil and gas industries and as inhibitors for complexation of heavy metals in natural gas compositions.

Keywords: Terminal alkynes, aliphatic, aromatic, cyclic and heterocyclic ketones, nucleophilic coupling, product yield.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the world, the oil and gas, chemical, rubber-technical, textile, and pharmaceutical industries are considered the main driving forces of the economy, and the synthesis of numerous new preparations for the development of these fields is of great importance. In particular, the wide utilization of acetylenic alcohols in the oil and gas, chemical, rubber-technical, textile, and pharmaceutical industries for obtaining high-quality preparations is highly significant. Currently, in developed countries, systematic research is being conducted on the synthesis methods [1-4] and production technologies of acetylenic alcohols and their

derivatives that possess biological activity, including aliphatic, aromatic, cyclic, and heterocyclic substituents. The research aims to investigate their physical, chemical, energetic, and mechanical properties, chemical transformations, and activities, as well as to improve the methods for producing new ionites, biocides, inhibitors, solvents, and polymers based on them in the industry [5-8].

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Avance (400 and 100.6 MHz, respectively) spectrometer at 20-25 °C in CDCl₃, acetone-d₆, C₆D₆, solution using the solvent line as an internal reference; IR spectra of the synthesized compounds

of rings in the ketone molecule, the size of radicals, and their impact on the reaction and product yield was established. According to the findings, the reactivity decreased in the order of acetophenone < methyl ethyl ketone < cyclopentanone < cyclohexanone < methylbutanone < methyl isopropyl ketone < methyl- β -naphthyl ketone < methyl-p-tolyl ketone < methyl cyclobutyl ketone < methyl furyl ketone < methyl pyridinyl ketone < camphor < adamantane < methyl thienyl ketone < methyl mesityl ketone < methyl-2-thioxophenyl ketone. Kinetic parameters of the investigated reactions were determined, the activation energies for the formation of aromatic acetylenic alcohols were identified, the specific properties of the synthesized compounds were characterized, including their electronic structure, distribution of charges within the molecule, quantum chemical, and molecular dynamics properties.

The synthesized terminal acetylenic alcohols were utilized as inhibitors to separate sulfur compounds from the composition of natural gas products at the "Muborak Gas Processing Plant" JSC. This method enabled the separation of 42-58% of elemental sulfur, hydrogen sulfide, mercaptans, sulfides, and disulfides, which are hazardous sulfur compounds, from the composition of natural gas products, thus improving the quality of natural gas, reducing the amount of toxic sulfur compounds emitted into the environment, and increasing the operational reliability and durability of technological equipment and facilities. The application of the synthesized acetylenic alcohols was also recommended for their use as agents in the rubber and technical industry, providing an effective means of suppressing the agglomeration of sulfur compounds and improving resource efficiency and ecological safety.

The inhibitory properties of the synthesized aromatic acetylenic alcohols against components that form salt deposits in circulating water systems in industrial plants were investigated. The water hardness of the "Ohangaron Cement" JSC circulating water systems was determined. Experiments were conducted with solutions of aromatic acetylenic alcohols at concentrations of 5.0-25.0 mg/l. The results indicated the effective inhibitory activity of aromatic acetylenic alcohols against components that form salt deposits in circulating water systems, with a selective retention of metal cations (87.0%). Aromatic acetylenic alcohols were utilized as inhibitors against the formation of salt deposits in

circulating water systems at the "Ohangaron Cement" JSC.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the nucleophilic addition reaction of various natural ketones with aliphatic and aromatic terminal alkynes was investigated, and the influence of different catalysts under specific conditions was studied. Based on the obtained results, a new catalytic system, $Zn(OTf)_2/TBAF \cdot 3H_2O$, is proposed for the efficient synthesis of acetylenic alcohols.

REFERENCE

- [1] Uma Maheshwar G., Jhillu S.Y. Synthesis of Chiral Propargyl Alcohols Following the Base-Induced Elimination Protocol: Application in the Total Synthesis of Natural Products // *New Journal of Chemistry*, 2020. Volume 44, №13, pp. 4972-4986.
- [2] Jade V., Maria J. Gonzalez S., Nicholas C. and Beatriz M. Catalytic Enantioselective Addition of Alkylzirconium Reagents to Aliphatic Aldehydes // *Molecules*, 2021. Volume 26, pp. 4471-4499.
- [3] Robert P., Maciej S. and Jacek M. Propargylation of CoQ0 through the Redox Chain Reaction // *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 2022. Volume 87, pp. 683-692.
- [4] Pei Zh., Qihong H., Yuyu Ch., Rongshi L., Pengfei L., Wenjun L. Remote Stereocontrolled Construction of Vicinal Axially Chiral Tetrasubstituted Allenes and Heteroatom-Functionalized Quaternary Carbon Stereocenters // *Organic Letter*, 2019. Volume 21, №2, pp. 503-507.
- [5] Bowen J., Xiangyu Y., Yong X., Natalya L., Heriberto D.V., Yanyan G., Ye Y. and Francis V. Tandem Reactions Based on the Cyclization of Carbon Dioxide and Propargylic Alcohols: Derivative Applications of α -Alkylidene Carbonates // *Catalysts*, 2022. Volume 12, №1, pp. 1-35.
- [6] Jiang S., Du S., Yang R., Jin F., Zhou Z.-Z., Tian W.-F., Song X.-R. and Xiao Q. Brønsted Acid Promoted Sulfonylation of Propargylic Alcohols: Synthesis of Triaryl Allenyl Sulfones under Mild Conditions // *European Journal Organic Chemistry*, 2023. e202201377.
- [7] Hao An, Shifei Liu, Shao-Jie Wang, Xiaoyi Yu, Chenqi Shi, Haonan Lin, Si Bei Poh, Hui Yang, Ming Wah Wong, Yu Zhao, Zhifeng Tu, and Shenci Lu. Kinetic Resolution of Acyclic Tertiary Propargylic Alcohols by NHC Catalyzed Enantioselective Acylation // *Organic Letters*, 2024. Volume 26, Issue 3, pp. 702-707.
- [8] Kentaro Iwaki, Koki Maruno, Osamu Nagata, and Norio Shibata. Ethynyl-SF₄-Pyridines: Reagents for SF₄-Alkynylation to Carbonyl Compounds // *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 2022. Volume 87, Issue 9, 6302-6311.
- [9] Ziyadullaev O., Otamukhamedova G., Ikramov A., Abdurakhmanova S., Boytemirov O. Synthesis Of Aromatic Acetylene Alcohols Using Complex Catalytic Systems // *Chemistry and Chemical Engineering*, 2021. №2, pp. 58-72.
- [10] Michal R., Stanislaw L., Piotr K. Highly Enantioselective Addition of Phenylethynylzinc to Aldehydes Using Aziridine-Functionalized Tridentate Sulfinyl Ligands // *Tetrahedron: Asymmetry*, 2010. Volume 21, pp. 2687-2689.

- [11] Chen Sh.-Y., Liu W., Wu. X., Ying J., Yu X., Pu L. A Lewis acid activated reaction of Zn with EtI to promote highly enantioselective alkyne additions to aldehydes // *Chemical Communication*, 2015. Volume 51, pp. 358-361.
- [12] Zhang A.-L., Yang L.-W., Yang N.-F., Liu D.-C. Investigation of catalytic activity and catalytic mechanism of chiral amino diol tridentate ligands in the asymmetric addition of aldehydes in the presence of methyllithium reagent // *Journal of Organometallic Chemistry*, 2014. Volume 768, pp. 50-55.
- [13] Bauer T. Enantioselective dialkylzinc-mediated alkynylation, arylation and alkenylation of carbonyl groups // *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, 2015. Volume 299, pp. 83-150.
- [14] Moore D. and Pu L. BINOL-Catalyzed Highly Enantioselective Terminal Alkyne Additions to Aromatic Aldehydes // *Organic Letters*, 2002. Volume 4, №11, pp. 1855-1857.
- [15] Gao G., Xie R.-G., and Pu L. Highly enantioselective alkyne additions to aldehydes in the presence of 1,1-bi-2-naphthol and hexamethylphosphoramide. // *The Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2004. Volume 101, №15, pp. 5417-5424.
- [16] Xiao-Pu Fu, Li Liu, Dong Wang, Yong-Jun Chen, Chao-Jun Li "On water"-promoted direct alkynylation of isatins catalyzed by NHC-silver complexes for the efficient synthesis of 3-hydroxy-3-ethynylindolin-2-ones // *Green Chemistry*, 2011. Volume 13, Issue 3, pp. 549-553.
- [17] Pierre de Fremont, Natalie M. Scott, Edwin D. Stevens, Taramatee Ramnial, Owen C. Lightbody, Charles L. B. Macdonald, Jason A. C. Clyburne, Colin D. Abernethy, Steven P. Nolan Synthesis of Well-Defined N-Heterocyclic Carbene Silver(I) Complexes // *Organometallics*, 2005. Volume 24, Issue 26, pp. 6301-6309.
- [18] Taramatee Ramnial, Colin D. Abernethy, Mark D. Spicer, Iain D. McKenzie, Ian D. Gay, Jason A. C. Clyburne A Monomeric Imidazol-2-ylidene-Silver(I) Chloride Complex: Synthesis, Structure, and Solid State ¹⁰⁹Ag and ¹³C CP/MAS NMR Characterization // *Inorganic Chemistry*, 2003. Volume 42, Issue 5, pp. 1391-1393.
- [19] Karen J. Ardila-Fierro, Carsten Bolm, Jose G. Hernandez Mechanosynthesis of Odd-Numbered Tetraaryl[n]cumulenes // *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 2019. Volume 58, Issue 37, pp. 12945-12949.
- [20] Konstantin S. Rodygin, Yulia A. Vikenteva, Valentine P. Ananikov Calcium-Based Sustainable Chemical Technologies for Total Carbon Recycling // *Chemistry-Sustainability-Energy-Materials*, 2019. Volume 12, Issue 8, pp. 1483-1516.
- [21] Otamuxamedova G.Q., Ziyadullayev O.E., Shmid E., Maniecki T. Enantioselective alkynylation of some cyclical ketones by 3,3'-diphenylbinaphthol dilithium // *Chemical and Chemical Engineering*, 2019. 2, pp. 30-36.
- [22] Отамухамедова Г.К., Зиядуллаев О.Э., Буриев Ф.Х., Аблакулов Л.К. Алкилирование некоторых кетонов в присутствии октина-1 / Всероссийская научная школа-конференция "Марковниковские чтения: Органическая химия От марковникова до наших дней", 2024. С. 86